

Synthesis and Biological Activities of 1,1'-Bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)cyclohexane

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1,1'-Bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)cyclohexane have been synthesized. Most of the compounds exhibit promising antibacterial activity and moderate antifungal activity.

Bisphenols are useful as bactericides, disinfectants, agricultural fungicides, antioxidants, drugs for treatments of seborrhea, acne and anti-inflammatory agents^{1,2} The toxicity of the phenolic compounds can be minimized by converting phenolic group to an easily hydrolysable ester group. Bisphenol phosphates are also used as insecticides and miticides³. Esters of bisphenols² are active at low concentration but dimethyl ether and dioxyacetic acids are inactive even at high concentrations. The literature survey on bisphenols containing cardo group especially cyclohexyl group² revealed scanty work on esters of cardo-bisphenols which prompted us to investigate biological activities of 1,1'-bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted-phenyl)cyclohexane (1).

1 R₁ = R₂ = H
2 R₁ = R₂ = Br
3 R₁ = R₂ = Cl
4 R₁ = CH₃, R₂ = H

R, R' and R'' may be

5 2-Cl
6 3-Cl
7 4-Cl
8 3-NO₂
9 4-NO₂
10 2-OH
11 2-OH and 3,5-NO₂
12 3,5-NO₂
13 3-CH₃
14 4-CH₃
15 2,4-OH
16 3,5-OH
17 4-I

Results and Discussion

Physical and spectral data of the compounds are reported in Table 1. Infrared spectra displayed bands at 1748-1686 (C=O) and 1289-1250 cm⁻¹ (C-O) besides normal modes of the alkane, alicyclic and aromatic groups.

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND PMR SPECTRAL DATA OF 1-17

Compd. no.	M.p., °C/ (% yield)	δ
1	140 (71)	1.514 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.198 (4H, s, α-CH ₂), 7.145-6.567 (8H, m, ArHBC), 7.534-7.35 (6H, m, ArH), 8.183-8.069 (4H, m, ArH)
2	182 (61)	1.502 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.154 (4H, s, α-CH ₂), 7.566-7.219 (10H, m, ArH BrBC+ArH), 8.274-8.174 (4H, m, ArH)
3	132 (67)	1.470 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.156 (4H, s, α-CH ₂), 7.196-6.762 (4H, m, ArH ClBC), 7.494-7.240 (6H, m, ArH), 8.176-7.966 (4H, m, ArH)
4	146 (69)	1.485 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.161 (10H, s, α-CH ₂ + CH ₃), 7.194-6.655 (6H, m, ArH MeBC), 7.548-7.426 (6H, m, ArH), 8.235-8.105 (4H, m, ArH)
5	162 (78)	1.475 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.154 (4H, s, α-CH ₂), 7.414-6.608 (16H, m, ArH BC+ArH)
6	146 (82)	1.470 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.159 (4H, s, α-CH ₂ -), 7.123-6.618 (8H, m, ArH BC), 7.467-7.317, 8.267-7.867 (8H, m, ArH)
7	185 (84)	1.473 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.144 (4H, s, α-CH ₂), 7.128-6.636 (8H, m, ArH BC), 7.448-7.306 (4H, m, ArH), 8.06-7.766 (4H, m, ArH)
8	145 (69)	1.456 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.152 (4H, s, α-CH ₂), 7.199-6.611 (8H, m, ArH BC), 7.733-7.399, 8.4-8.3 (8H, m, ArH)
9	182 (72)	1.465 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.139 (4H, s, α-CH ₂ -), 7.116-6.603 (8H, m, ArH BC), 8.647-8.207 (8H, m, ArH)
10	90 (88)	1.461 (6H, s, β+γ-CH ₂ -), 2.167 (4H, s, α-CH ₂), 7.55-6.60 (12H, m, ArH BC+ArH), 8.317-8.067 (6H, m, ArH + OH)

NOTE

Table-1 (contd.)

11	137 (67)	1.465 (6H, s, $\beta+\gamma$ -CH ₂ -), 2.154 (4H, s, α -CH ₂), 7.104-6.581 (8H, m, ArH BC), 7.45 (4H, s, ArH), 8.233 (2H, s, OH)
12	180 (76)	1.473 (6H, s, $\beta+\gamma$ -CH ₂ -), 2.149 (4H, s, α -CH ₂), 7.109-6.581 (8H, m, ArH BC), 8.5-8.4 (2H, d, ArH), 9.177-9.11 (4H, d, ArH)
13	180 (45)	1.438 (6H, s, $\beta+\gamma$ -CH ₂ -), 2.129 (10H, s, α -CH ₂ + CH ₃), 7.106-6.598 (8H, m, ArH BC), 8.639-8.561 (8H, m, ArH)
14	180 (49)	1.417 (6H, s, $\beta+\gamma$ -CH ₂ -), 2.08 (4H, s, α -CH ₂), 2.364 (6H, s, CH ₃), 6.967-6.817 (12H, m, ArH BC + ArH), 7.238-7.78 (4H, d, ArH)
15	135 (51)	1.466 (6H, s, $\beta+\gamma$ -CH ₂ -), 2.157 (4H, s, α -CH ₂), 7.109-6.596 (8H, m, ArH BC), 7.881-7.270 (10H, m, ArH + OH)
16	132 (48)	1.466 (6H, s, $\beta+\gamma$ -CH ₂ -), 2.152 (4H, s, α -CH ₂), 7.110-6.601 (12H, m, ArH BC + ArH), 7.473 (2H, s, ArH)
17	185 (80)	1.473 (6H, s, $\beta+\gamma$ -CH ₂ -), 2.133 (4H, s, α -CH ₂), 7.114-6.606 (8H, m, ArH BC), 8.208-7.478 (8H, m, ArH)

Antibacterial and antifungal activities : All compounds (1-17) were screened against different strains of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria such as *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Salmonella typhosa*, *Staphylococcus citreus* and *Aspergillus niger* by using cup-plate method⁴. The solvent used was DMF and the sample concentration was 50 μ g.

It is observed that **3** (17 mm) has comparable activity with ampicillin against *S. typhosa* (17 mm), while **1**, **2**, **4-8**, **10**, **11** and **17** (14-15 mm) have moderate activity and the rest have poor activity against same organism. It has also been observed that **1-7**, **9-13**, **15** and **17** (20-26 mm) have moderate to comparable activity with norfloxacin (26 mm), chloramphenicol (24 mm) and ampicillin (24 mm) against *E. coli*, and **8**, **14** and **16** (18-19 mm) have poor activity against same microbes **1-9**, **11**, **12**, **16** and **17** (20-22 mm) have moderate to comparable activity with chloramphenicol and ampicillin against *S. citreus* (33 mm) while others have poor activity. It is interesting to note that **5**, **6**, **8** and **16** (18-20 mm) have comparable activity with ampicillin (17 mm) against *B. mega* and moderate activity against norfloxacin (23 mm) against same microbes. **1-17**

(15-19 mm) have moderate activity with griseofulvin (23 mm) against *A. niger*.

Experimental

M.p.s. were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were scanned on a Shimadzu DR-1, 435-IR spectrophotometer and pmr spectra on a Hitachi R-1200 (60 MHz) using deuterio chloroform or the mixture of deuterio chloroform and dimethyl sulfoxide, and TMS as an internal standard.

All the chemicals and solvents used were purified according to the literature processes. Precoated silica gel plates were used for analytical tlc.

1,1'-Bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexane (BC), 1,1'-bis(3-methyl-4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexane (MeBC), 1,1'-bis(3,5-dichloro-4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexane (ClBC) and 1,1'-bis(3,5-dibromo-4-hydroxyphenyl)cyclohexane (BrBC) were synthesized according to the reported methods⁵. Substituted benzoyl chlorides were synthesized by refluxing a mixture of substituted benzoic acids (0.1 mol) and thionyl chloride (0.15 mol) for 4 h and the excess thionyl chloride distilled off. 1,1'-Bis(*p*-substituted-benzoyloxy-substituted phenyl)cyclohexane were synthesised from bisphenols (0.1 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (25 ml) containing pyridine (2-3 drops) as catalyst and to which benzoyl chloride (0.1 mol) in 1,4-dioxane (25 ml) was added dropwise and the mixture was refluxed for 4 h. It was then poured in crushed ice and the resulting esters (**1-17**) were washed with bicarbonate solution and distilled water, dried at 50° and recrystallized from methanol-water. The purity of compounds was checked by tlc using ethyl acetate-n-hexane (3 : 7, v/v).

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